

METABOLIC CHANGES IN THE BODY OF PATIENTS WITH CHOLESTATIC SYNDROME

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The issues of early diagnosis of liver diseases accompanied by cholestasis and their differential diagnosis are still very relevant, since the possibilities of studying the function of bile formation and bile production are limited by determining the severity of cholestasis, and are based on clinical manifestations and the determination of biochemical markers [1,2].

The purpose of the study: to study the biochemical parameters of blood in cholestatic syndrome.

Materials and methods: The study included 90 people, aged 40-74 years, living in the region of the city polyclinic No. 1 in Bukhara. The main group consisted of 60 patients with cholestatic syndrome (CHS), the control group consisted of 30 conditionally healthy individuals. The diagnosis was verified according to the requirements of the World Health Organization (WHO), classified according to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10).

Results and discussion.

To study the state of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, a biochemical blood test was performed in all patients with CHS.

The analysis of morning fasting glucose of y women in the studied groups showed values at the reference level in both y women of group 1 - 5.2 ± 0.13 g/l, and y women of group 2 - 5.2 ± 0.29 g/l, with a significant increase against the control - 4.8 ± 0.1 g/l ($p < 0.005$).

The study of the blood lipid spectrum showed an increase in the level of total cholesterol in women of group 1 to 5.9 ± 0.08 mmol/l, and to 6.6 ± 0.16 mmol/l in women of group 2 with a significance against the indicators of the control group - 5.31 ± 0.13 mmol/l ($P < 0.05$).

Analysis of LDL levels in women with CHS it showed a significant increase to 4.0 ± 0.09 mmol/l in women of the 1st group, $p < 0.05$, and to 4.0 ± 0.06 mmol/l in women of the 2nd group against the control - 2.3 ± 0.82 mmol/l.

Consequently, the data obtained show the active transport of cholesterol and lipids at the cellular and tissue levels in the early stage of the development of HC in women.

The study of HDL levels showed y values for women at the control level: in the 1st group up to 1.8 ± 0.04 mmol/l and in the 2nd group up to 2.1 ± 0.05 mmol/l, which is 1.7 ± 2.4 mmol/l at the control level.

In studies of y women in both groups, values at the level of the control group were shown: - 1.56 ± 0.8 mmol/l in group 1, and 1.4 ± 0.2 mmol/l for y women in group 2, against the control- 1.34 ± 0.04 mmol/L.

A comparative analysis of the obtained data from biochemical blood tests of women with indicators of men of the appropriate age showed a significant increase in glucose to 5.3 ± 0.29 g/l in group 1 and to 6.7 ± 0.37 g/l in group 2 of men ($p < 0.05$).

Men also have a statistically significant increase in total cholesterol to 5.7 ± 0.09 mmol/l in group 1 and up to 5.9 ± 0.09 mmol/l in group 2 against the control- 4.7 ± 0.29 mmol/l, $p < 0.05$.

A significant increase in LDL in y men, regardless of the type of HC, was found to 3.9 ± 0.07 mmol/l in group 1, to 4.0 ± 0.06 mmol/l in group 2, with respect to control - 2.1 ± 0.12 mmol/l, $p < 0.05$.

A statistically significant increase in HDL levels in men of group 1 was found up to 2.2 ± 0.07 mmol/l and up to 2.1 ± 0.09 mmol/l for men of the 2nd group against the control values- 1.2 ± 0.19 mmol/l, $p < 0.05$.

This upward trend is noted in relation to the values of TG y in men of the 2nd group to 1.8 ± 0.14 mmol/l versus the control values- 1.2 ± 0.2 mmol/l, $p < 0.05$. Consequently, in men with intrahepatic cholesterol, there is an increase in the level of TG in the blood, which requires nutrition monitoring for the use of products containing TG.

The analysis of liver damage markers for differential diagnosis of the genesis of CHS showed an increase in the level of gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (GGTP) by 2.34 times in women of group 1, and 24.2 times in women with HC of group 2 against the control- 12.3 ± 2.2 u/l, ($P < 0.05$).

There is also an increase in the level of alkaline phosphatase (alkaline phosphatase) in CHS y of group 2 women by 6.14 times ($P < 0.05$) against the control-up to 40.1 ± 1.3 u/l. The A y of the women of group 1 of the alkaline phosphatase was at the level of the control values with a tendency to increase: 43.5 ± 3.45 u/l and 40.1 ± 1.3 u/l, respectively.

A comparative assessment of the studied blood parameters of y men selected for the study showed a significant increase in the level of total bilirubin to 19.6 ± 0.77 mmol/l in y men of group 1 and to 24.0 ± 0.43 mmol/l in y men of group 2 against the control - 14.2 ± 0.66 mmol/L.

At the same time, there was a statistically significant decrease in the level of the ALT enzyme in y men of group 1 to 27.2 ± 1.10 u/l ($P < 0.05$), and in y men of group 2 to 29.4 ± 0.86 u/l versus control- 31.2 ± 0.2 u/l.

The AST of y men with CHC was at the level of control indicators, and y men of the 2nd group revealed a statistically significant increase to 26.6 ± 1.04 u/l versus the control- 24.2 ± 0.11 u/l, $P < 0.05$.

The Rhytis coefficient (AST/ALT) was at the level of the control normal values (0.77) of y men in both groups: 0.94 and 0.90, respectively, which shows the absence of liver damage in y men with CHC.

GGTP in men of group 1 with HCV was increased by 2.29 times ($P < 0.05$), and by 13.6 times in men of group 2 compared to control values- 22.3 ± 1.2 units/l, $P < 0.05$.

The activity of alkaline phosphatase in CHC in y men was also increased by 1.35 times in y men of group 1 ($P < 0.05$) and 6.48 times in y men of group 2 ($P < 0.001$) against the control - 38.1 ± 1.3 u/l.

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of the obtained results of blood biochemistry in women with CHC y confirms a violation of bilirubin metabolism and an increase in the Rhytis coefficient to 1.45 y in women with extrahepatic CHC (group 1). With intrahepatic cholesterol in women, there is a higher increase in the level of GGTP and alkaline phosphatase, which is due to liver damage of any etiology. It was found that cholestatic syndrome in women occurs against the background of an increase in LDL and activation of lipid transport to organs with the formation of visceral fat. In men, the mechanism of development of cholestatic syndrome is associated with the development of hyperglycemia and dyslipidemia.

References:

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